

WATER QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF A PERENNIAL POND OF MUZAFFARPUR (BIHAR – INDIA)

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Abstract

In recent years due to rapid urbanization, industrialization, and modern agricultural activities, the quality of water bodies deteriorated causing environmental hazards. The present study was intended to calculate water quality index (WQI) of a perennial pond of Muzaffarpur, in order to ascertain the quality of water for public use and other purposes. The study was carried out for a period of one year. Water quality monitoring has one of the highest priorities in environmental protection policy. Water quality index (WQI) indicating the water quality in terms of index number, offers a useful representations for overall quality of water for public or for any intended use as well as in the pollution abatement programs & in water quality management. A number of parameters affect the usability of water for a particular purpose. In this study WQI was determined for the rainy, winter and summer seasons on the basis of various physic-chemical parameters such as pH, dissolved oxygen, total alkalinity, hardness, etc.

Keywords: *physic-chemical parameters, WQI, perennial pond, environmental hazards.*

Introduction – Water is one of the most important factors for every living organism in this planet. There is no life without water. The fresh water bodies such as ponds and lakes are the most important sources of water for human activities are being threatened as a consequence of development activities. These water bodies not only mirror their environment, but also reflect the human society around them. The quality of water is getting vastly deteriorated due to unscientific waste disposal, improper water management and carelessness towards environment, which has also led to scarcity of potable water affecting the human health (Agarkar, S.V; 2003). Water resources available for drinking and other domestic purpose must possess high degree of purity, free from chemical contamination and microorganisms (Borul et al 2012). In India there are enormous number of natural and man-made water bodies used for various purposes, including drinking and agriculture. However, in recent years, due to rapid urbanization, industrialization and modern agricultural activities, the quality of water bodies deteriorated causing environmental hazards (Bhadja, P et al 2013). The large scale urban growth due to increase in population and migration of population from rural areas to urban centers have increased domestic effluents while industrial development manifested either due to setting up of new industries or expansion activities resulting in generation of copious volume of industrial effluents (Avinash & Saksena 2010). Water quality monitoring has one of the highest priorities in environment protection policy (Pesce and Wunderlin, 2000. Simeonov et al 2002) to control and minimize the incidence of pollutant oriented problems and to provide water of appropriate quality to serve various purposes such as drinking water supply, irrigation, recreational, industrial and to protect the valuable fresh water resources to safeguard public health (Bartram et al 2002). Ascertaining the quality is crucial before use for various purposes (Sargaonkar & Deshpande, 2003, Khan et al. 2003).

Water quality index of ponds and lakes have been studied by several workers viz. Horton (1965), Shardendu and Ambasht (1988), Yogendra and Puttaiah (2008), Umamaheshwari (2010) etc. Water quality index provides a single number that expresses overall water quality at a certain location and objective of water quality index is to turn complex water quality data into information that is understandable and usable by the public. A single number cannot tell the whole story of quality; there are many other water quality parameters that are not included in the index. However, a water quality index based on some very important parameters can provide a simple indicator of water quality.

Study Area:

Muzaffarpur district popularly known as land of litchi is situated in Bihar, at the bank of Budhi Gandak River. It has numerous lentic water bodies. It lies between north latitude 25⁰54' to 26⁰ 23' and east longitude 84⁰ 53' to 85⁰ 45'. In the present investigation, a perennial pond popularly known as Kanhauli Math Pokhar was selected for assessing the quality of water. This pond is about 62m in length and 60m in width. The approximate area is 3000 sq m. The pond particularly receives domestic wastes and other wastes throughout the year.

Materials and Methods:

Collection of water:

The water samples were collected from Kanhauli Math Pokhar at regular intervals for one year and analyze for physico-chemical parameters. For collection purpose plastic bottles of 1 liter capacity were used. After collection of water sample, bottles were labeled properly and then brought to laboratory for study.

Water Analysis:

Physico-chemical analysis of the sample was done according to Standard Methods as per American Public Health Association (APHA 1998, 2005), Vijyan V.S. (1991), Golterman (1978), and Trivedi & Goel (1984). pH was determined on spot. For conformation it was analyzed again using buffer solution in laboratory. Rest of the parameters such as Dissolved oxygen (DO), Biological oxygen demand (BOD), Alkalinity, Hardness, Total dissolved solids (TDS), Magnesium, Calcium were studied in the laboratory as per the standard procedures of APHA.

Water Quality Index (WQI):

The water quality index has been calculated by using the standards of drinking water quality recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO), Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS), and Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR).

Calculation:

The weighted arithmetic index method has been used for calculation of WQI of the water body. Quality rating or sub index (qn) was calculated by following formula:

$$qn = 100 (Vn - Vio) / (Sn - Vio).$$

Where:

qn = quality rating for the nth water quality parameter.

Vn = Estimated value of the nth parameter at a given sampling station.

Sn = Standard permissible value of nth parameter.

Vio = Ideal value of nth parameter in pure water.

Ideal value in most cases $V_{10} = 0$ except in certain parameters such as pH and dissolved oxygen. The calculation of quality rating for pH and DO ($Vn \neq 0$) is 7.0 and 14.6 mg / l respectively.

Unit weight was calculated by a value inversely proportional to the recommended standard values (Sn) of the corresponding parameter.

$$W_n = K / S_n.$$

Where: W_n = Unit weight for the nth parameters.

S_n = Standard values for nth parameters.

K = Proportionality constant.

The overall water quality index was calculated by aggregating the quality rating with the unit weight linearly.

$$W.Q.I. = \sum W_n \cdot q_n / \sum W_n.$$

Table 1. Water quality index (WQI) and status of water quality. (Chatterjee & Raziuddin).

Water Quality Index	Water Quality Status
0-25	Excellent water
26-50	Good water
51-75	Poor water
76-100	Very poor water
> 100	Not suitable for drinking

Table 2. Drinking water standards, recommending agencies and unit weight.

S. No.	Parameters	Standards	Recommended agencies	Unit Weight
1	pH	6.5-8.5	ICMR, BIS	0.2188
2	Total Alkalinity (TA)	120 mg / l	ICMR,	0.0155
3	Total Hradness (TH)	300 mg/ l	ICMR, BIS	0.0062
4	Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)	500 mg / l	ICMR, BIS	0.0037
5	Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	5.0 mg / l	ICMR, BIS	0.3723
6	Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD)	5.0 mg / l	ICMR,	0.3723
7	Calcium	75 mg / l	ICMR, BIS	0.025
8	Magnesium	30 mg/ l	ICMR, BIS	0.062

Result & Discussion:

The seasonal variation of the physico-chemical prameters of the pond water and water quality index of three different seasons (winter, summer & rainy) have been presented in Table 4, 5, 6. In the present work the water

quality index (WQI) of the pond is calculated from eight very important physico – chemical parameters, in three different seasons. pH is one of the most important factors that serve as an index for the pollution. The average pH value of the pond water was 7.3 during rainy season, 7.9 during winter season, and 8.00 during summer. However, when the average values for three seasons are taken in to account the water body under observation was found to be slightly alkaline. This finding is in agreement with Yogendra & Puttaiah (2008), Sinha (1995), Swarnalatha & Narasinga Rao (1993), Shardendu & Abbasht (1988), Petre (1975), who have also made similar observations in their studies on different water bodies. In my study higher values of alkalinity registered during summer. The observed average values of total alkalinity during rainy season, winter season and summer season were 58 mg/ l, 76 mg/ l & 80 mg/ l respectively. According to USPHA the maximum permissible limit is 120 mg / l. The low alkalinity during rainy season may be due to dilution, while the higher values during summer season may be due to the presence of excess of free CO₂ products as a result of decomposition process coupled with the mixing of sewage and domestic waste. Jain et al (1996) also reported similar finding in the study of the Halali reservoir.

Hardness was found 166 mg / l during rainy season, 178 mg / l during winter and 184 mg / l during summer. Higher values found during summer season. According to Mohanta and Patru (2000) addition of sewage, detergents and large scale human use might be the cause of elevation of hardness. The hardness of water beyond 300 mg/ l causes gastrointestinal irritation (ICMR, 1975).

Presence of dissolved oxygen (DO) in water may be due to direct diffusion from air and photosynthetic activity of autotrophs (Shanthik et al. 2002). The average dissolved oxygen also varies from season to season. The oxygen content of natural water bodies varies with temperature, salinity etc. The concentration of dissolved oxygen regulates the distribution of flora & fauna. Dissolved oxygen below 2 mg / l may lead to fish mortality. DO values were higher in those ponds where good aquatic life present. Biochemical oxygen demand is a parameter to assess the organic load in a water body. The increased levels of BOD indicate the nature of chemical pollution. In my study the BOD was found higher (33 mg / l) in summer season. During rainy and winter seasons the average BOD was 28 mg / l & 31 mg / l respectively.

Table 3. Seasonal variation in the physico–chemical parameters of perennial Pond (Kanhauli Math Pokhar).

Parameters	Season		
	Rainy	Winter	Summer
pH	7.3	7.9	8.00
Total Alkalinity (mg /l)	58	76	80
Total Hardness (mg / l)	166	178	184
Total dissolved solids (mg / l)	581	461	580
Dissolved Oxygen (mg /l)	7.27	7.45	6.75
Biological Oxygen Deemand (mg /l)	28	31	33
Calcium	43.89	44.26	46.83
Magnesium	44.39	41.18	44.81

The observed average value of magnesium was 44.39 mg/l in rainy season, 41.18 mg/l during winter season and 44.80 mg/l during summer season. Magnesium hardness particularly associated with sulphate ion has laxative effect

on persons unaccustomed to it (Khursid, 1998), while the observed average value of calcium was 43.89 mg/l during rainy season, 44.26 mg/l during winter season and 46.83 mg/l during summer.

From the result it is clear that the water quality index (WQI) of the pond is higher in summer season, which indicates that the water is not suitable. Even though WQI value found relatively less in winter & rainy season, the water quality is very poor.

Table 4. Calculation of water quality index of pond water in rainy season.

Parameters	Observed value (Vn)	Standard value (SN)	Unit Weight (wn)	Quality rating (qn)	Wn. Qn
pH	7.3	6.5-8.5	0.2188	54.23	11.86
TA (mg / l)	58	120	0.0155	48.53	0.7522
TH (mg /l)	166	300	0.0062	55.33	0.343
TDS (mg / l)	581	500	0.0037	116.00	0.43
DO (mg / l)	7.27	5.00	0.3723	83.58	31.11
BOD (mg / l)	28	5.00	0.3723	133.33	49.63
Ca (mg / l)	43.89	75	0.025	59.12	1.48
Mg (mg / l)	44.39	44.39	0.062	149.00	9.24
			$\sum Wn = 1.0758$	$\sum qn = 699.12$	$\sum Wn.qn = 104.85$
Water quality Index = $\sum Wn.qn / Wn = 104.85 / 1.0758 = 97.46$					

Table 5. Calculation of water quality index of pond water in winter season.

Parameters	Observed value (Vn)	Standard value (Sn)	Unit Weight (Wn)	Quality Rating (qn)	Wn.qn
pH	7.9	6.5-8.5	0.2188	55.35	12.11
TA (mg / l)	76	120	0.0155	65.33	1.012
TH (mg / l)	179	300	0.0062	58.73	0.364
TDS (mg / l)	461	500	0.0037	95.2	0.352
DO (mg /l)	7.45	5.00	0.3723	79.58	29.62
BOD (mg / l)	31	5.00	0.3723	136.44	50.80
Ca (mg / l)	44.26	75	0.025	59.67	1.49
Mg (mg/l)	41.18	30	0.062	137.25	8.5
			$\sum Wn = 1.0758$	$\sum qn = 687.55$	$\sum Wn.qn = 104.25$
Water quality Index = $\sum Wn.qn / Wn = 104.25 / 1.0758 = 96.90$					

Table 6. Calculation of water quality index of pond water in summer season.

Parameters	Observed value (Vn)	Standard value (Sn)	Unit Weight (Wn)	Quality Rating (qn)	Wn.qn
pH	8.00	6.5-8.5	0.2188	56.75	12.42
TA (mg / l)	80.00	120	0.0155	67.10	1.04
TH (mg / l)	184.00	300	0.0062	66.33	0.411
TDS (mg / l)	580.00	500	0.0037	118.00	0.43
DO (mg / l)	6.75	5.00	0.3723	83.00	30.90
BOD (mg / l)	33.00	5.00	0.3723	158.45	59.00
Ca (mg / l)	46.83	75	0.025	63.28	1.58
Mg (mg / l)	44.80	30	0.062	149.79	9.29
			$\sum W_n = 1.0758$	$\sum q_n = 762.70$	$\sum W_n.q_n = 115.071$
Water quality Index = $\sum W_n.q_n / W_n = 115.071 / 1.0758 = 106.96$					

Conclusion: The physical & chemical properties of water fluctuate with season & interact with one another and have a combined effect on animals and plants living in it. The factors controlling the composition of natural waters are extremely varied and include physical, chemical and biological process. By studying physico – chemical parameters of the pond, it can be safely concluded that, the pond water is not suitable for drinking purpose, without prior treatment. The pond water shows the characters of eutrofication. It is also found that the pollution load is relatively higher during summer season when compared to rainy & winter season.

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